

Management and preservation of green spaces in Bukavu: Assessment of existing practices and exploration of future solutions

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Research

This study examines the management practices of green spaces in the city of Bukavu, highlighting their essential role in urban climate resilience and the maintenance of quality of life, particularly in terms of social cohesion and public health. It underscores the threats facing these spaces, mainly related to rapid and uncontrolled urbanization, sustained demographic growth, socio-spatial inequalities, and weak local governance. Based on semi-structured interviews conducted with local authorities, representatives of semi-public entities, and private actors in Bukavu, as well as a cartographic analysis of the years 1957, 2013, and 2025, the study shows a marked decline in green spaces, aggravated by natural disasters and unregulated land occupation. Despite their importance, the management of these spaces still faces many challenges, leaving them insufficiently protected. This situation calls for the adoption of sustainable and inclusive urban planning strategies in a context of high urban density.

In Bukavu, urban green spaces are vanishing under urban sprawl and weak governance, demanding collaborative planning for sustainable and inclusive city futures.

Urban green spaces, essential elements in building the sustainable cities of tomorrow, refer to areas reserved for nature within urban settlements. They include parks, urban forests, public and private gardens, landscaped areas, as well as all other natural zones that provide aesthetic benefits and leisure opportunities for city dwellers.

These spaces perform multiple functions in addressing contemporary urban challenges. They strengthen climate resilience by regulating temperature and offering natural solutions to the effects of climate change (Idverde, 2023), mitigate urban heat islands through shading and evapotranspiration (Röbbel, 2016), and sequester CO₂ to improve air quality and citizens' well-being (Isabelle, Nicola, Jean, & Rafael, 2018; Mair, 2020; WHO, 2016). Furthermore, they support economic and social development by increasing land value and urban attractiveness (UN-Habitat, 2013), while fostering social inclusion through accessible public spaces for all (Lee & Maheswaran, 2011; Röbbel, 2016).

However, the management of green spaces remains a major challenge in many countries due to limited budgets, political and administrative constraints, and climate uncertainties (Rivière, 2020; Jim, 2020; Dacheux-Auziere & Marchand, 2024). Moreover, the growing trend of privatization restricts accessibility and deepens social inequalities, with residents of disadvantaged neighborhoods rarely benefiting from quality spaces or being consulted in development projects (Martin, 2021;

Lefèvre & Maillard, 2019; Wolch, Byrne, & Newell, 2014).

In the Democratic Republic of Congo, as in many African cities, the management and preservation of urban green spaces are rarely among the priorities of local authorities. The case of Bukavu, a city located in the east of the country, particularly illustrates this situation. Since the country's independence, this 60 km² city (Ndyababo et al., 2010) has faced multiple urban challenges (Marhegane, Ndagano, Ntasma, Winlondja, & Byombuka, 2022). Its urban transformation, marked by rapid population growth accompanied by chaotic land occupation, has deeply disrupted citizens' lifestyles, leading to increased land speculation (Bisoka, Mudinga, & De Herdt, 2021; Loteens, 2019) and failures in construction and urban planning (Nkuba, Kabagale, Mugisho, & Ndele, 2024). In a context of urban densification and the absence of effective urban policies, these dynamics have caused the encroachment and privatization of numerous public urban spaces (Mushizi, 2023), particularly green spaces, whether public gardens, urban forests, or landscaped areas along roads and roundabouts.

In light of these observations, and given the importance of green spaces in addressing environmental challenges and improving urban quality of life, this study is framed within collaborative planning theory. It explores how different actors (residents, public authorities, organizations) use green spaces, in order to understand the logics of their design, occupation, and management processes.

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Bukavu's green heritage under threat: Displacement, land pressure, and informal urbanization drive the disappearance of urban commons.

Mapping of green spaces in the city of Bukavu, 1957

Mapping of green spaces in the city of Bukavu, 2013

Mapping of green spaces in the city of Bukavu, 2025

Evolution of the surface areas of the city of Bukavu between 1957 and 2025

In the years preceding the independence of the Democratic Republic of Congo, Bukavu was distinguished by abundant vegetation, covering about two-thirds of its surface. This dominance of green spaces earned the city the nickname "Green Bukavu." This natural heritage was

evident both in the vegetation lining the main arteries—such as Avenue Patrice E. Lumumba and the roads radiating from Independence Square—as well as on the wooded slopes (Ruzizi, Mukukwe, Kabwakasire, etc.), which gave the city a certain environmental quality.

However, this landscape configuration has gradually been challenged by a series of combined dynamics. Rapid population growth, coupled with informal urbanization, has encouraged the progressive occupation of previously vegetated areas. This phenomenon has been amplified by population displacements caused by regional insecurity and recurring natural disasters, such as heavy rainfall and landslides.

Neighborhoods like Nyakaliba, Nkafu, and Kazaroho illustrate this trend, with displaced households settling in areas once considered urban green reserves. This process reflects a slow but steady erasure of natural elements in favor of spontaneous urban forms, revealing the inability of planning systems to regulate urban expansion in a context of multiple vulnerabilities.

Since 2013, growing land pressure, combined with often deficient urban governance regarding green space preservation, has accelerated their decline across all communes of Bukavu. This period has been marked by an intensification of subdivision practices, sometimes illegal or tolerated, even in areas officially reserved for their ecological or landscape value, such as the shores of Lake Kivu (Vedaste & Kelly, 2019).

Urban vegetation cover is thus experiencing a continuous decline, reflecting a transition toward an increasingly dense and functionally unbalanced urban fabric. Several green spaces have either been seized for private purposes or progressively transformed, illustrating an opportunistic appropriation process of urban commons.

Who Manages Bukavu’s Green Spaces? Local Authorities, Semi-Public Entities, and Households Shape a Fragile Urban Balance

The urban challenges that Bukavu has faced for several decades, notably population growth and the uncontrolled occupation of land, have influenced management modes and compromised efforts to preserve green spaces. In this context, three modes of green space management, each associated with a specific type of actor, have been identified: The first concerns management by local authorities, where urban authorities plan and undertake maintenance actions and, in some cases, finance green spaces; the second is management by semi-public entities such as educational institutions and religious organizations as well as some private actors who take charge of

developing these spaces; and finally, individualized domestic management, where households create and maintain their own green spaces autonomously, without coordination with local authorities.

In recent decades, initiatives to create green spaces, particularly gardens and amusement parks, have been undertaken by private actors in Bukavu. However, the management of green spaces, whether developed or not, remains largely dominated by semi-public entities. These hold more than 75% of the vegetated surfaces and natural areas of the city.

Actors and Green Spaces Managed by Semi-Public Entities in Bukavu

No.	District	Neighborhoods	Managing Semi-Public Entities
1	Kadutu	Nkafu, Nyakaliba, Karhale (Nyakaliba)	Institut Supérieur de Développement Rural de Bukavu, Université Catholique de Bukavu, Economat Général Bukavu, Centre Psychiatrique SOSAM, Pharmakina, Lycée Wima, Université Officielle de Bukavu, Institut Supérieur Médical, Coordination des Écoles Conventionnées Catholiques, Institut Technique Fundi Maendeleo
2	Ibanda	Nyalukemba, Ndendere, Panzi	Centre Spirituel Amani, Collège Alfajiri, Institut Supérieur Pédagogique and its affiliated school, Athénée d’Ibanda, Cercle sportif de Labotte, Paroisse St Jean Baptiste Cahi, Centre Xavérien Solidarité, Hôpital de Panzi, Institut Technique Avenir, Université Evangélique en Afrique
3	Bagira	Lumumba, Kasha	Institut Bwindi, Institut de Bagira

Green spaces management in Bukavu: Legal gaps, budget constraints, and weak policies fuel urban degradation

In Bukavu, the management of green spaces faces numerous challenges. On the side of local authorities, these include administrative and legal ambiguity resulting from the absence of an official inventory listing the city's green spaces, increasing budgetary constraints due to the lack of resources allocated to their maintenance, and a mismatch between urban development and management practices.

On the side of private actors and semi-public entities, there is the progressive dispossession of green spaces and their replacement by infrastructure. Beyond the budgetary constraints and the growing privatization of green spaces already documented in the literature (Martin, 2021), other challenges arise in urban areas. These include divergences between ecological objectives and citizens' expectations, particularly concerning the

choice of plant species or types of landscaping (Rivière, 2020), as well as often inappropriate urban planning policies (Dupont, 2022). Observations carried out between 1957 and 2025 in Nkafu, Karhale, and Bwindi reveal management confronted with many challenges, notably uncontrolled land occupation, which has led to the gradual disappearance of green spaces in Bukavu. However, taking into account their socio-ecological and economic benefits, several initiatives have been undertaken since the colonial period to improve their management in the Democratic Republic of Congo

In the absence of accompanying measures, several initiatives have had only limited impact, giving way, over time, to an increased degradation of green spaces, aggravated by natural disasters and strong real estate pressure in Bukavu and elsewhere in the country.

Initiatives Undertaken in Favor of Green Space Management Between 1957–2025

No.	Years	Initiatives Undertaken
1	June 1957	Urban Planning Decree, Belgian Congo
2	July 1973	Zairianization Law affecting the management and orientation of spaces at the national level
3	January 2022	Presidential Ordinance No. 22/003 clarifying the attributions of ministries
4	July 2021	Urban Reference Plan of the city of Bukavu
5	October 2023	Adoption of the Land Use Planning Law by the National Assembly

Green spaces in Bukavu: Essential for health, culture, and urban attractiveness, yet marked by inequality and fragile access

Green spaces play a fundamental role in air purification, maintaining the microclimate, and supporting cultural activities in Bukavu. According to the United Nations, green spaces contribute to the prevention of stress-related diseases by improving the quality of life of city dwellers (UN, 2016).

They offer numerous physical and psychological benefits (Lee & Maheswaran, 2011) and constitute an effective strategy for mitigating health risks of mortality and morbidity linked to heat, particularly in regions with

greater vegetation cover (Nazish, Kiran, & Emmama, 2024).

In the context of Bukavu, their sound management would further enhance the city's attractiveness and territorial marketing while offering citizens social benefits related to leisure and public health. Nevertheless, access to vegetated areas, whether developed or not, belonging to semi-public entities as well as private individuals, remains conditional in Bukavu. Very few specific users and urban families access them for leisure.

The rest of the population, particularly those in poorer neighborhoods, hardly access them at all. These social inequalities in access to green spaces, a reality in many cities worldwide, were documented by Gregory (2024). According to him, despite the contribution of green spaces to reducing heat-related deaths, populations in disadvantaged neighborhoods benefit the least.

In a context of urban densification, efforts must be made toward sustainable management of green spaces in Bukavu to anticipate their total disappearance. Thus, three groups of actions, based on recommendations from representatives of public

authorities and interviewed experts, can be considered: (i) encourage vertical construction in order to free up space for the creation of new green spaces accessible to all; (ii) reintroduce into Bukavu's urban mindset the concept of "leisure," one of the fundamental functions of the city that has been forgotten (in modern urbanism, living, working, circulating, cultivating oneself, and leisure were identified as fundamental functions of a city by Le Corbusier (Corbusier, 1945)); (iii) implement urban public policies that protect and enhance existing green spaces and promote reforestation of non aedificandi sites.

Bukavu's green spaces: From sharp decline to the urgent need for inclusive and collaborative urban policies

This study has examined current practices in the management and preservation of green spaces in the city of Bukavu. By cross-referencing cartographic data—particularly photographs of Bukavu from 1957, 2013, and 2025—with the perspectives of local authorities, experts, and users, the results confirm a clear reduction in surface area and the disappearance of many green spaces between 1957 and 2025, passing through 2013.

The main reasons are the cycles of natural disasters experienced by Bukavu, uncontrolled urban population growth, unregulated land occupation, as well as irresponsible practices surrounding the management of these spaces by public authorities, semi-public entities, and private actors. The study shows that green spaces

contribute to improving the quality of life of Bukavu's residents by stabilizing local temperatures, purifying the air, and sustaining cultural activities. However, the rush to occupy the remaining green spaces for urbanization, the legal ambiguity surrounding their management, and disparities among communes in terms of coverage, access, and use by citizens underscore the urgent need for inclusive and equitable urban policies based on collaborative planning. Further research is necessary to better understand the perceptions of Bukavu's inhabitants toward green spaces, the imperatives for creating new landscaped areas, and the ecological performance of existing spaces, in order to contribute to the sustainable urban transformation of Bukavu.

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